

Case Report**Detection of Foreign Bodies by Using Computed Tomography in a Cat**Emine Merve Alan^{1*}, Cansu Aslan Çataklı², Lora Koenhems³

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Abstract

A 3 year-old domestic shorthair female cat was presented with a history of, persisted vomiting, anorexia and listlessness. In the anamnesis, when the owner was persistently asked whether the cat ate a foreign body, the answer was always no. The presence of tenderness was detected on abdominal palpation. In the complete blood cell count and routine serum biochemical analyzes, no abnormality was detected except for leukocytosis, thrombocytopenia and a slight increase in glucose level. Radiographic and ultrasonographic imaging were performed, but because of suspicious areas in radiographic and ultrasonographic imaging, computed tomography (CT) was decided. A foreign body was detected in the colon as a result of CT and the foreign bodies were surgically removed. It was determined that foreign bodies were door handle protector and rubber buckle. This case is presented to show that advanced imaging techniques such as CT are more effective in detecting suspicious foreign bodies in the gastrointestinal tract and to contribute to the literature.

Keywords: Foreign body, cat, computed tomography

Introduction

Gastrointestinal obstruction is a common occurrence for cats present with signs of gastrointestinal disease. There are many causes of obstruction in small animals, such as gastrointestinal linear foreign bodies, focal intestinal neoplasia, trichobezoars. Clinical signs of gastrointestinal obstruction include vomiting, diarrhea, anorexia, constipation, weight loss, tenesmus and many more (MacPhail, 2002). Clinical findings vary depending on the localization, degree and duration of the obstruction. Gastrointestinal obstruction causes disturbances in fluid-electrolyte and acid-base balance. Foreign bodies can cause complete or partial obstruction. In general, complete obstruction is associated with a more rapidly developing general condition disorder, while partial

obstruction is more associated with chronic maldigestion and malabsorption findings (Papazoglou et al., 2003; Hayes, 2009).

Abdominal palpation is an important examination method when gastrointestinal obstruction is suspected. However, diagnosis usually requires diagnostic imaging methods such as radiography, ultrasonography, contrast studies, and endoscopy. The definitive diagnosis is made by laparotomy (MacPhail, 2002). In recent years, computed tomography has also been used in the diagnosis of gastrointestinal obstruction. CT has played an important role in diagnosis in veterinary medicine since its introduction (Ohlerth and Scharf, 2007; Hounsfield, 1973).

Case History

A 3-year-old female domestic cat was brought to Istanbul University-Cerrahpasa, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Department of Internal Medicine with complaints of loss of appetite, weakness and vomiting for 3 days (Figure 1). In the clinical history, the owner insisted that her cat did not eat any foreign body.

Figure 1. Image of the general condition of the cat during the clinical examination

The patient underwent clinical examination, routine blood analysis (complete blood count (CBC) and serum biochemical analyzes), and diagnostic imaging. The presence of tenderness was detected on abdominal palpation in the physical examination. In the CBC and serum biochemical analyzes; leukocytosis, lymphocytosis, monocytosis, thrombocytopenia and a slight increase in glucose and lipase level were detected (Table 1 and Table 2).

Table 1. Results of complete blood count analyzes

Parameters	Results	References
RBC (M/ μ L)	9.48	6.54 – 12.2
HCT (%)	39.9	30.3 – 52.3
HGB (g/dl)	14	9.8 – 16.2
MCV (fL)	42.1	35.9 – 53.1
MCH (pg)	14.8	11.8 – 17.3
MCHC (g/dl)	35.1	28.1 – 35.8
RDW (%)	23.2	15.0 – 27.0
RETIC (K/ μ L)	10.4	3.0 – 50.0
WBC (K/ μ L)	25.7	2.87 – 17.02
NEU (K/ μ L)	9.5	2.30 – 10.29
LYM (K/ μ L)	13.55	0.92 – 6.88
MONO (K/ μ L)	2.14	0.05 – 0.67
EOS (K/ μ L)	0.31	0.17 – 1.57
PLT (K/ μ L)	83	151 – 600
MPV (fL)	15.5	11.4 – 21.6
PCT (%)	0.13	0.17 – 0.86

Table 2. Results of serum biochemical analyzes

Parameters	Results	References
BUN (mg/dL)	17	16-36
CREA (mg/dL)	0.7	0.8-2.4
PHOS (mg/dL)	3.5	3.1-7.5
ALT (U/L)	49	12-130
ALKP (U/L)	32	14-111
GGT (U/L)	0	0-4
TBIL (mg/dL)	0.5	0.0-0.9
AMYL (U/L)	1283	500-1500
LIPA (U/L)	1471	100-1400
TP (g/dL)	6.5	5.7-8.9
GLU	193	74-159
ALB (g/dL)	3.3	2.2-4.0
GLOB (g/dL)	3.3	2.8-5.1
ALB/GLOB	1	

A suspected area in the abdomen was detected on the radiographic examination, however, since this area could not be distinguished from feces based on this image, it was decided to perform an ultrasonographic (USG) examination (Figure 2). A hyperechoic region with a distal shadowing was found in the colon on the the USG. However, since the diagnosis of foreign body could not be made exactly in the animal, it was decided to perform computed tomography (CT) instead of experimental laparotomy due to the patient’s owner decision. As a result of CT, the presence of foreign body in the colon was confirmed (Figure 3-4).

Figure 2. Lateral radiographic image of the cat. Yellow arrow: suspicious area from foreign body.

Figure 3. Axial section of CT. Yellow arrow: Foreign body.

Figure 4. Saggital section of CT. Yellow arrow: Foreign body.

The foreign bodies were surgically removed. It was determined that foreign bodies were door handle protector and rubber buckle (Figure 5-6). A parenteral broad-spectrum antibiotic (Ceftriaxone 25 mg/kg IM q12 hours) and fluid therapy with lactated Ringer's solution for 7 days was started to the cat after the surgery. No food was given for the first 24 hours. The cat hospitalized for a week. After the discharge, only fat free liquid foods were given for a week.

Figure 5-6. Surgical removal of foreign bodies.

Discussion

Gastrointestinal foreign bodies are common in small animals. The general condition of the patient varies according to the size and shape of the foreign body and the duration of the obstruction. Vomiting, loss of appetite, abdominal pain and dehydration are the most common symptoms in cases of gastrointestinal obstruction (MacPhail, 2002; Bebchuk, 2002). In this case report, the patient had complaints of vomiting, anorexia and abdominal pain.

Diagnostic imaging frequently used in this patients and radiography is usually the first method used to diagnose foreign bodies. However, foreign bodies with low opacity are difficult to detect by radiography (Bebchuk, 2002). In these cases, advance diagnostic methods such as ultrasonography, endoscopy and computed tomography are used if suspicion still persists according to the anamnesis and clinical examination results (Ohlerth and Scharf, 2007; Baydar et al., 2021).

Ultrasonographic examination may be preferred later, since it does not require anesthesia, noninvasive, relatively easy method and a useful complementary imaging technique. It is also a better method than radiography in detecting radio-opaque objects. However, one of the limitations of this imaging method is excessive gas accumulation due to obstruction in the gastrointestinal tract may interfere with ultrasonographic examination. In addition, the ultrasound experience of the physician is important in diagnosing the foreign body (Tyrrell and Beck, 2006; Chavhan et al., 2004).

Endoscopy is a method that can be used to detect and remove foreign bodies in the upper gastrointestinal tract. However, in this case, the foreign body was not in a position to be removed by endoscopy (Baydar et al., 2021). For this reason, CT, one of the advanced imaging techniques, was used for diagnosis of the cat.

Leukocytosis and electrolyte imbalance are the most common hematologic abnormalities in these cases (Bebchuk, 2002). In a 2003 study, it was reported that 3 dogs with linear foreign bodies in the gastrointestinal tract had leukocytosis (Hoffmann, 2003). According to this, a mild leukocytosis was detected in our case as well. Electrolyte values could not be measured due to the financial situation of the patient's owner. It is known that there is a close relationship between leukocytes and platelets in case of inflammation (Gorbet and Sefton, 2004). It was thought that the thrombocytopenia seen in the blood result of our patient was formed as a result of inflammation. In the

Studies have shown that stress factor may cause hyperglycemia in cats (Opitz, 1990). In this case, the patient had also mild hyperglycemia and it was thought that the reason for this was stress. Koenhemi et al. (2011), diagnosed a dog with foreign body in their case report, and stated that the dog had thrombocytopenia and hyperglycemia similar to this case.

It is an issue that clinicians constantly discuss that which diagnostic procedure is more effective in detecting foreign body. It is valuable to make the definitive diagnosis non-invasively before the diagnostic laparotomy. In addition, as a result of these methods, the location of the foreign body in the gastrointestinal tract is determined, helping to perform the operation more quickly and easily. Therefore, tomography is an expensive but reliable diagnostic method compared to other imaging methods. This case is presented to show that advanced imaging techniques such as CT are more effective in detecting suspicious foreign bodies in the gastrointestinal tract and to contribute to the literature.

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